

Impact of Extraction Techniques on Bioactive Compounds and Antioxidant Potential from Date Palm Leaves

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ABSTRACT

The genus Phoenix is one of the most widely cultivated groups of palms around the world. In this study, we have evaluated the antioxidant activity and total phenolic compounds by using various in vitro systems and analysis of marker compounds by High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) of leaves extracts of *Phoenix dactylifera* L obtained by classical, ultrasonic assisted and Soxhlet method. The total phenolic content, flavonoids and tannin were determined by a spectrophotometric method. Total antioxidant activity expressed by reducing Mo (VI) to Mo (V) and DPPH radical scavenging methods were applied to test the antioxidant activities. The results indicated that the extract obtained by the ultrasonic assisted method extraction showed the highest total contents of phenolic. The antioxidant activities also found to be highest with the ultrasonic assisted method extract followed by other extraction techniques (Soxhlet and classical method). The results suggest that the leaves of the *Phoenix dactylifera* L can be considered as a good source of natural antioxidant, that we can use these natural extracts as food additives in replacement of synthetic compounds

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INTRODUCTION

Free radicals are chemically unstable atoms that cause damage to lipid cells, proteins and DNA as a result of imbalance between the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and the antioxidant enzymes¹. They are known to be the underlying cause of oxidative stress which is grossly implicated in the pathogenesis of various diseases such as cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, aging and metabolic syndrome. Examples of these radicals include superoxide anions, hydroxyl, nitric oxide and hydrogen peroxide radicals². An antioxidant, which can quench reactive free radicals, can prevent the oxidation of other molecules and may have healthpromoting effects in the prevention of degenerative diseases³. The interest in antioxidants has been increasing because of their high capacity in scavenging free radicals related to various diseases⁴. Many plants contain substantial amounts of antioxidants and can be utilized to scavenge the excess free radicals. The protection offered by different edible plants against oxidative stress in several diseases has been attributed to various antioxidants and vitamins. Potential antioxidant properties of the dietary phenolic compounds and flavonoids present in various fruits and vegetables have recently been

recognized in a number of investigations^{5,6}. The date palm (*Phoenix dactylifera* L., Areaceae) is one of mankind's oldest cultivated plants. It is highly popular worldwide, particularly in the Middle East and North Africa⁷. Different extraction techniques, such as classical, Soxhlet and ultrasonic extraction, are widely used for obtaining extractive substances from *Phoenix dactylifera* L. As a novel technique, ultrasonic extraction has recently been shown to be very promising and effective for obtaining bioactive substances. The main benefits of the use of ultrasound are the increase of the extraction yield, a faster process and even the improved quality of the extracts⁸. The aim of present works is to study in vitro antioxidant activities of the acetone extracts of *Phoenix dactylifera* L obtained by different methods extraction, using PPM and DPPH radical scavenging assays. In addition, the total phenolic content, flavonoids and condensed tannin from plant extracts were also measured.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Origin of plant material

The *Phoenix dactylifera* L were collected from southeast of Algeria, state of El Oued on December 2013. The leaves then separated from each other, washed and dried at room

temperature. All these organs were ground to a powder with a basic electric grinder and stored in the dark at room temperature before use. *Extraction of plant material*

Classical extraction

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Figure 1: Chromatograms of standard mixture (a), classical extraction (b), ultrasound extraction (c) and Soxhlet extraction (d). Peak 1: Ascorbic acid; Peak 2: Chlorogenic acid; Peak 3: Caffeic acid; Peak 4: Vanillin; Peak 5: Rutin. (c)

(d)

Ground plant material (15 g) and 70% Acetone (90 ml) were put in a series of the Erlenmeyer flasks (150 ml), and the ratio of plant material mass (g) to solvent volume (ml) was 1:8. No additional stirring was applied. The extraction was performed at 25°C for 24h. At the end of the extraction cycle the liquid extract was separated from the solid residue by vacuum filtration. The solid residue was washed twice with fresh solvent (20 ml). The filtrates were collected and the solvent was evaporated in a rotary vacuum evaporator at 40°C. Extracts were stored at +4 °C in dark until use.

Ultrasound extraction

Ultrasonic apparatus from Branson (40 kHz, 1500W, dimension 49 cm×14 cm×15 cm) was used for accelerated extraction. A beaker was partially submerged in an isothermal water bath to maintain the extraction temperature at 25°C. Fifteen grams (15 g) leaves were then extracted with 70% Acetone (90 ml) for 60 min. The extract was filtered through Whatman paper on a Büchner funnel by vacuum; the solids were washed with an additional 60 ml of ethanol. The filtrate was rotaryevaporated under

vacuum at 40°C to dryness. The crude extracts were dried in a vacuum oven at 40 °C. Extracts were stored at +4°C in dark until use.

Soxhlet extraction

The ground plant material (15 g) and 70% Acetone (90 ml) were taken into the Soxhlet apparatus, and were extracted for 6 hours. Previously, we found that the yield of extractive substance was not increased after that time. The liquid extract was evaporated under vacuum at 40 °C to constant mass. Extracts were stored at +4 °C in dark until use.

Evaluation of antioxidant activity Determination of total antioxidant activity

The total antioxidant activity of the extracts was estimated by the phosphomolybdenum method. This method was based on the reduction of MO (VI) to MO (V) by the extract and the formation of a green phosphate/MO (V) complex at acid pH⁹. An aliquot of 0.2 mL of the sample solution was mixed with 2.0 mL of the reagent solution (600 mM sulfuric acid, 28 mM sodium phosphate, and 4 mM ammonium molybdate). The reaction mixture was incubated at 95°C for 60

minutes and absorbance was measured at 695 nm against a blank contained 2 mL of reagent solution. Total antioxidant activity was expressed equivalent to gallic acid¹⁰.

DPPH radical scavenging activity

The radical scavenging activity using free-radical DPPH assay was carried out using the spectrophotometric method¹¹. An aliquot (1mL) of each extract was added to 2 mL of daily prepared acetone DPPH solution (0.1mM). The mixture was shaken gently and left to stand at room temperature in the dark for 15min. Thereafter, the absorbance was read at 515 nm. The scavenging activity was measured as the decrease in absorbance of the samples versus DPPH standard solution. Results were expressed as radical scavenging activity percentage (%) of the DPPH radical according to the formula: %DPPH radical scavenging = $[(A_0 - A_s)/A_0] \times 100$ Where A_0 is the absorbance of the control and A_s is the absorbance of the sample. The effective concentration having 50% radical inhibition activity (IC_{50}), expressed as mg extract/ mL, was determined from the graph of the free radical scavenging activity (%) against the extract

concentration¹². All results are means \pm SD.

Phytochemical investigation

Determination of total phenolic content (TPC) The total phenolic contents in all organs were determined by the Folin-Ciocalteu method¹³. Diluted acetone extracts (0.2 ml) was mixed with 1 ml of (10%) Folin-Ciocalteu reagent. After 5 min, 0.8 ml of 7.5% sodium carbonate solution was added to the mixture and incubated for 30 min at the 27 ± 2 °C. Absorbance was measured at 765 nm on spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800, Japan). Total phenolic content was standardized against gallic acid and expressed as milligrams of gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per gram of the sample¹⁴.

Determination of total flavonoid content (TFC) The total flavonoid content in extracts was determined spectrophotometrically¹⁵. Briefly, 1 mL of 2% aluminum trichloride ($AlCl_3$) acetone solution was mixed with the same volume of extract solution. The absorbance values of the reaction mixtures were determined at 415 nm after 10 min duration against a blank. Rutin was used as the standard and the total flavonoids content of the extracts was expressed as mg rutin equivalents per gram of extract ($mg RE g^{-1}$ extract)¹⁶.

Determination of condensed tannin content (CTC) CTC was determined by a miniaturised procedure¹⁷. Firstly, a 10 μ l acetone solution of samples, catechin or blank were introduced in wells. After wards a 4% vanillin acetone solution (120 μ l) was added, followed by addition of

concentrated HCl (60 μ l). The red mixture was allowed to stand for 15 min and the absorbance was measured at 500 nm using a microplate spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-1800, Japan). Results were expressed in mg of catechin equivalents/g of dry extract (mg CE/g). All samples were analysed at least three times¹⁸.

HPLC analysis

The composition of the extracts was analyzed by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC)¹⁹. We used a Shimadzu (LC 20A, Japan). System comprised of a 2LC10AT pump (A&B), a CTO-20A column oven, a SPD-20A UV-DAD detector and CBM-20A interface. A LC-18 column (150 mm x 4.6 mm i.d. x 5 mm) was employed. Samples were injected. The components of the samples were separated by gradient elution at at 30 °C. The mobile phases were: A, 98:2 (v/v) acetic acid, and B, acetonitrile and the elution gradient was: 0–5 min, 5% B; 10 min, 10% B; 11 min, 20% B; 20 min 20% B; 30 min 40% B; 40 min 50% B; 50 min 80% B. The flow rate was 1 ml/min and the detection wavelength was 300 nm. Phenolic compound standards Ascorbic acid, Chlorogenic acid, Vanillin, Caffeic acid and Rutin were dissolved in solvents extraction and used for identification of the phenolic acids present in different extracts of *Phoenix dactylifera* L. Peak identification in HPLC analysis was achieved by comparison of retention time and UV spectra of reference standards. Quantification of individual phenolic compounds in the extracts was done using the peak area of reference compounds and reported as mg/g of extract.

Statistical analyses

The data obtained in this study were expressed as the mean of three replicate determinations plus or minus the standard deviation (SD). Statistical comparisons were made with Student's test. *P* values <0.05 were considered to be significant.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the present study, three extraction methods were used to evaluate the total phenolic contents, total flavonoids, condensed tannin contents and antioxidant activity of leaves extracts from *Phoenix dactylifera* L. Among the different solvent extraction methods, successive Soxhlet extraction could provide comparable or even better results than the maceration and ultrasonic assisted for extracting phenolic compounds and showed a significant antioxidant activity over the other two methods. Nowadays, several novel extraction techniques such as sonication and microwave-assisted have been developed and employed along with conventional extraction techniques for the extraction of bioactive compounds and nutraceuticals from plants²⁰.

Total phenolic, flavonoid and condensed tannin contents Phytochemicals are increasingly accepted as health

promoting, maintaining and repairing agents in cells, tissues, or the whole human body. The phytochemicals that are frequently associated with human health are polyphenols, carotenoids and tocopherols. Polyphenols are the major secondary metabolites in most plants

Table 3: Constituents content analysed by HPLC.
 $y = 82773x - 14238$ ($r^2 = 0.99$) and $y = 24113x - 10605$ ($r^2 = 0.996$), where y was the peak area and x was the concentration of analytes. The quantitative results are summarized in Table 3. As shown, ascorbic acid was the most dominant constituent and similar in the different extracts. All The extracts obtained by different techniques are contains five compounds.

CONCLUSION

In this study, *in vitro* antioxidant activities, phenolic, flavonoids and tannin contents of leaves extracts from *Phoenix dactylifera* L obtained by classical, Soxhlet and ultrasonic assisted methods have been evaluated. The results indicated that ultrasound extract exhibited strongest antioxidant activities and the contents of polyphenols. The highest content of flavonoids was obtained by classical extract than those by other extraction methods. This study explained the advantage of the ultrasound, compared to the conventional extraction methods both for polyphenols, was similar since polyphenols yield obtained with a lower solvent consumption and a shorter extraction time.

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